

PROCEDIN

Building Procurement Capability for Embedding and Driving Innovation

D4.1

Database of European education provision

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PROCEDIN

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
WP	Work package
POI	Procurement of Innovation
GM	Green Mobility
CE	Circular Economy
PERFECT	Purchasing Education Research For European Competence Transfer
MOOC	Massive Online Open Course
PSM	Purchasing and Supply Management

1 Summary

The growth of procurement and attracting future leaders can be enhanced through the visibility of procurement education. With the goal to map procurement education, PROCEDIN surveyed universities across Europe. The project partners compiled data on European universities that provide master's or bachelor's level education in procurement, sustainability, and entrepreneurship. In the present database, there are 114 different universities from 27 different countries, which together offer 1679 courses. In order to make sure that the courses are updated and kept current, PROCEDIN will publish an online survey where respondents can recommend both new courses that should be added to the database and revisions to the database.

2 Introduction

2.1 Aim

In work package (WP) 4, Future Leaders, PROCEDIN's objectives are to engage the university community and educate, inspire and attract talent to the procurement field. One way is to connect entrepreneurs, procurement professionals, sustainability experts, cities and students with procurement of innovation (POI) education, and POI for circular economy (CE) and green mobility (GM) specifically. Visibility of procurement education is key in the development of procurement and attracting future leaders. Therefore, PROCEDIN surveys European universities to map procurement education. In this deliverable, the project partners collated information on European universities which offer masters or bachelor level education on procurement, sustainability and entrepreneurship.

We envision that (procurement, sustainability and innovation) practitioners can use the database for connecting to educators in their region, whereas it can provide students (and educators) with visibility on procurement courses within Europe. In this deliverable, the focus is on the database itself. Task 4.2 is about designing routes for engagement, which will set out various pathways for engagement, including advice to different stakeholder groups on how to make good use of the database.

3 Method

In surveying European universities to map procurement education, the PROCEDIN team applied four different strategies, which we explain below.

3.1 Strategy 1

The first step in creating a database of European education provision, was to check existing efforts by previous projects. The PERFECT (Purchasing Education Research For European Competence Transfer) project (project number 2015-1-DE01-KA203-002174), finished in 2018, aimed to develop a MOOC (Massive Online Open Course) and an empirically validated European curriculum for purchasing and supply management (PSM).¹In their efforts, they collected information on purchasing masters and bachelors in Europe, in 2017. Their database consisted of 18 different universities, in five different

¹ More information on the PERFECT project can be found on: <http://www.perfect.lfo.tu-dortmund.de/>

countries. Whereas PERFECT provided course programs (multiple courses comprised for one degree), the PROCEDIN database consist of courses (singular entities). Consequently, the procurement, sustainability and entrepreneurship courses offered by these universities in their programs are incorporated in our database (see Table 2 for an overview of all universities).

3.2 Strategy 2

The second strategy included an online search for purchasing courses in European universities ranked in the top 200 universities worldwide.² For each of the European universities, the *first* step included finding a course finder of the university. *Secondly*, if a course finder could be found, researchers searched for the keywords ‘procurement’ and ‘purchasing’. If the university offered courses with ‘procurement’ and/or ‘purchasing’ in the course name or course abstract, the courses were included in the database. If there no courses on procurement or purchasing, the researchers would move on to the next university. If the university would have purchasing and/or procurement courses, the *third* step would include searching for the following keywords: supply, sustainability, innovation, entrepreneurship and contract(ing). These courses are also included in the database. This extra overview provides additional information of the universities which provide next to the procurement courses, also provides entrepreneurship and sustainability expertise. This second strategy led to 30 universities, from 10 different countries. Table 1 provides an overview of the top 200 ranked European universities who provide procurement and/or purchasing courses, whereas Table 2 provides an overview of all universities in the database.

Table 1: Top 200 universities with purchasing and/or procurement courses

Country	Universities
United Kingdom	King's College London, University of Liverpool, University of Birmingham, University of Leeds, The University of Sheffield, Newcastle University, University of Exeter,
Switzerland	ETH Zurich, University of Zurich, University of Lausanne, University of Bern
Germany	Technical University of Munich
Denmark	Technical University of Denmark (DTU), University of Copenhagen (UCPH), Aarhus University (AU)
Sweden	Lund University, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Uppsala University, Stockholm University
Norway	University of Oslo, University of Bergen
Finland	University of Helsinki
Netherlands	Leiden University, University of Twente, University of Groningen, Eindhoven University
Austria	Technische Universität Wien, University of Vienna
Italy	Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna
Ireland	University College Dublin

² <https://www.topuniversities.com/university-rankings/world-university-rankings/2022> was used to distinguish the top 200 universities (filtered on Europe)

3.3 Strategy 3

The purchasing and procurement courses found through strategies one and two, came from 11 different European countries, with nations such as Belgium, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain notably missing. Therefore, the network of the PROCEDIN team was utilized to find purchasing courses in regions that are currently under-represented. The three strategies combined let to 1679 courses, from 114 universities, from 27 countries (see Table 2).

Table 2: Overview of universities within the database

Country	University
Albania	Agricultural University of Tirana University of Tirana
Andorra	University of Andorra
Austria	University of Vienna Technische Universität Wien
Azerbaijan	Azerbaijan State Economic University
Belarus	Belarusian Trade and Economic University of Consumer Cooperatives Belarusian State University
Belgium	KU Leuven
Bosnia and Herzegovina	University of Banja Luka
Bulgaria	Varna Free University Chernorizets Hrabar Southwest University Sofia University St.Kliment Ohridski Burgas Free University Higher School of Management
Croatia	University of Zagreb University of Dubrovnik
Czech Republic	University of Economics and Business Prague Czech University of Life Sciences Prague
Denmark	Aarhus University (AU) Aalborg University (AAU) Copenhagen Business School (CBS) IT University of Copenhagen (ITU) Technical University of Denmark (DTU) Roskilde University (RUC) University of Copenhagen (UCPH) University of Southern Denmark (SDU)
Finland	University of Helsinki University of Turku University of Jyväskylä University of Oulu University of Vaasa University of Eastern Finland Aalto University Tampere University
France	Universite PSL Audencia Business School
Germany	Anhalt University of Applied Sciences University of Augsburg

	University of Bamberg Free University of Berlin Humboldt University of Berlin Technical University of Berlin Bielefeld University Ruhr University Bochum University of Bonn Braunschweig University of Technology University of Bremen Jacobs University Bremen Chemnitz University of Technology Clausthal University of Technology Darmstadt University of Technology TU Dortmund University Technical University of Munich
Ireland	University College Dublin
Italy	Politecnico Milano Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna
Netherlands	Leiden University University of Twente University of Groningen Eindhoven University
Norway	BI Norwegian Business School The Arctic University of Norway Molde University College Norwegian School of Economics Norwegian University of Life Sciences Norwegian University of Science and Technology Nord University OsloMet - Oslo Metropolitan University University of South-Eastern Norway University of Agder University of Bergen University of Oslo University of Stavanger Western Norway University of Applied Sciences Volda University College Østfold University College
Portugal	University of Aveiro
Serbia	University of Belgrade Univeristy of Novi Sad
Slovakia	University of Economics in Bratislava Bratislava University of Economics and Management
Slovenia	University of Ljubljana
Spain	EADA
Sweden	Lund University KTH Royal Institute of Technology Uppsala University Stockholm University University of Gothenburg Umeå University

	Linköping University Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences Luleå University of Technology Karlstad University Örebro University Linnaeus University Mid Sweden University Malmö University
Switzerland	ETH Zurich University of Zurich University of Lausanne University of Bern
United Kingdom	King's College London University of Birmingham University of Leeds The University of Sheffield Newcastle University University of Exeter Cardiff University University of Liverpool University of Reading University of Aberdeen Robert Gordon University Salford University
Total: 27 countries	114 universities

3.4 Strategy 4: looking ahead

An important aspect of the PROCEDIN project is its view on continuity and generating its own self-sustaining momentum at project's end. To ensure that the courses will be updated and stay up-to-date, PROCEDIN will post an online questionnaire, in which respondents can indicate both new courses that should be added to the database, as well as changes to the database.

The survey can be found here: https://utwentebbs.eu.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_eg0ccKgLA6di84K. The survey consists of questions regarding (1) the name of the course, (2) the university offering the course, (3) the country, (4) the keyword that best describes the course, (5) the level of the course, (6) a course description, (7) the course language and (8) a possible website of the course. The survey will be shared with the PROCEDIN network, and will be posted on the PROCEDIN website, to ensure that the database can be continuously updated. For the duration of the project, the University of Twente will update the database every other month. Discussions on possible organizations, partnerships or research centers that could continue the continuity of the database after the project's end are ongoing.

4 Database

4.1 Database structure

The current database consists of an Excel file, that will be uploaded on PROCEDIN's website as a resource bank (<https://procedin.eu/resources/>). Interested parties are provided with multiple ways

to filter the courses and programs that are useful for them. Interested parties have the opportunity to filter courses and programs based on the (1) country, (2) the name of the university, or (3) the corresponding keyword (purchasing/ procurement/ innovation/ entrepreneurship/ sustainability). After finding a course and/or program that they are interested in, the interested party will be presented with a course/ program description and the link to the corresponding website. No personal or contact details are provided in the database, so no privacy issues will arise. The links that are provided in the database direct towards universities' own websites.

Country	University	Search words	Course name	Level	Course description	Language	Website
Belgium	KU Leuven	Purchasing	Supply Chain and Operatic	MSc	This course provid	English	https://onderwijsaanbod.kuleur
Belgium	KU Leuven	Procurement	Supply Chain Management	MSc	The main objectiv	English	https://onderwijsaanbod.kuleur
Belgium	KU Leuven	Purchasing	Purchasing and Supply Ch	MSc	Full 30 ECTS track	English	https://onderwijsaanbod.kuleur
Czech Repu	University of Economics	Purchasing	Purchasing	MSc	Teach students ab	English	https://insis.vse.cz/katalog/syll
Czech Repu	University of Economics	Purchasing	Purchasing and Supply	BSc	Teach students ho	Czech	https://insis.vse.cz/katalog/syll
Czech Repu	University of Economics	Procurement	Public Contracts and Public	MSc	The course is orie	Czech	https://insis.vse.cz/katalog/syll
Czech Repu	University of Economics	Procurement	Public Procurement and C	MSc	The course is orie	Czech	https://insis.vse.cz/katalog/syll
Czech Repu	Czech University of Life	Procurement	Economics for managers	MSc	The course deals v	English	https://www.pef.czu.cz/en/r-9
Denmark	Copenhagen Business Sc	Procurement	CASES in Strategic Manag	MSc	Understand and e	English	https://kursuskatalog.cbs.dk/20
Denmark	Copenhagen Business Sc	Procurement	Performance Measureme	MSc	Discuss how value	English	https://kursuskatalog.cbs.dk/20
Denmark	Aarhus University (AU)	Purchasing	Business-to-Business Purc	Cand	analysing, assessi	English	https://kandidat.au.dk/business
Denmark	Aarhus University (AU)	Purchasing	Regulating Marketing and	Cand	In this way, the st	English	https://masters.au.dk/business
Denmark	Aarhus University (AU)	Purchasing	Supply Chain Management	Cand	Knowledge of wor	English	https://masters.au.dk/operatio
Denmark	Aarhus University (AU)	Procurement	EU Competition and Procu	Cand	The aim of the cou	English	https://masters.au.dk/retailma
Denmark	Aarhus University (AAU)	Procurement	EU Public Procurement an	Cand	The students will	English	https://masters.au.dk/retailma
Denmark	Aalborg University (AAU)	Procurement	Outsourcing and Procure	MSc	The course focuse	English	https://moduler.aau.dk/course
Denmark	University of Copenhagen	Procurement	EU public procurement la	Cand	Undervisningen vil	Danish	https://kurser.ku.dk/course/jju
Denmark	University of Copenhagen	Purchasing	Real estate - purchasing, p	BSc	Fagets formål er	Danish	https://kurser.ku.dk/course/jjul
Denmark	Technical University of	Procurement	Sustainable Operations an	MSc	The course covers	English	https://kurser.dtu.dk/course/4
Denmark	Technical University of	Purchasing	Supply Chain Management	MSc	A student who has	English	https://kurser.dtu.dk/course/6
Finland	University of Helsinki	Procurement	Wood procurement - supp	MSc	To give an underst	English	https://studies.helsinki.fi/cours
Finland	University of Oulu	Procurement	Procurement and Supply (Advance	MSc	describe the vario	English	https://opas.peppi.oulu.fi/en/c
France	Audencia Business Scho	Purchasing	MSc Supply Chain & Purch	MSc	Created in 2009, t	English	https://master.audencia.com/e
Italy	Politecnico Milano	Procurement	Advanced procurement m	MSc	The course is desi	English	https://www.gsom.polimi.it/en
Italy	Politecnico Milano	Procurement	Supply Chain Strategy and	MSc	Specifically, the c	English	https://www.gsom.polimi.it/en
Portugal	University of Aveiro	Procurement	Supply Chain Management	MSc	Concepts of Suppl	Portuguese	https://www.ua.pt/en/uc/1040
Slovakia	University of Economics	Procurement	Public Procurement	MSc		English	https://jnhf.euba.sk/en/
Slovakia	Bratislava University of	Procurement	Public Administration	MSc	They offer a study	English	https://www.vseba.sk/en/Stu

4.2 Database descriptives

The current database consists of 27 countries, with 114 different universities, that combined offer 1679 different courses. Table 3 summarizes the different types of courses in the database.

Table 3: Database descriptives

Type of course	Number of courses
Purchasing & Procurement	194
Entrepreneurship	187
Sustainability	248
Innovation	368
Contract	64
Supply	157
Business	461
Total courses	1679

5 Next steps

PROCEDIN incorporates multiple strategies to ensure the best access and usability of the database:

Strategy 1: bundling forces. The Database of European education provision is not the only database in the PROCEDIN project. Deliverable 1.1 and 1.2 include a resource base for buyers and vendor firms. Combining these resources into one resource bank, allows for bundling of the currently existing resources, increasing the accessibility for existing materials to improve knowledge on responsible/sustainable and innovative procurement within the European Union. This combined database will be accessible on the PROCEDIN website from the end of June.

Strategy 2: active engagement. Encouraging POI includes active engagement between the students, educators, city procurement authorities and businesses. In task 4.2, PROCEDIN will offer those routes for engagement. PROCEDIN will run two events with 25+ participants bringing together POI leaders in buying organizations and other POI stakeholders (including if possible civil society organizations) with universities to promote and facilitate engagement. Parts of the events will be recorded and edited extracts made available with the guidance.

Strategy 3: continuity. For the duration of the project, the database will be updated every other month by the University of Twente. However, for PROCEDIN it is important that the resources outlive the project duration. Therefore, current conversations are ongoing with parties that could keep the database running after the project's end.